

Women and Management: Reflective Research on Women as Better Managers

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Abstract

The competency and skill of a manager remains same across gender. Women being dynamic in their personality, they fine tune their skills according to need of the hour. This makes them better managers in the organization. This reflective research highlights on the managerial skills of three women managers, their out of way management policies to empower their employees and value addition to their organizations. With reference to Robert L.Kartz three management skills approach, this article analyses how these women managers successfully converted their skills for organizations growth and how it is been converted as triumphant endeavor in the longer run.

Introduction

A manager is a person responsible for controlling or administering an organization or a group of staff towards defined goal of the entity. This happens with a set of skills which is called as management skills. This set of tried and tested skill sets help to plan, communicate, decide and co ordinate the work force towards an organizational goal.

As far as the workforce is concerned, half of women population is represented by 30% of work force. But, representation of women in management cadre is very negligible, if not nil. A study conducted at 2006 says that for every 100 men only 2 women get administrative or managerial role in India. The data released by Confederation of Indian Industry says, only 16% of women are junior managers, 4% are in middle and only 2% in senior level management. This shows a clear lag in women moving up in the ladder of an organization.

As suggested by Robert L.Kartz three skill management approach, the proportion of conceptual, technical and human skills varies as they move up in the cadre. This changing expertise demands a dynamic manager.

So, a manager is expected to shift roles according to the position he stands for.

Women as Managers

Do women lack these significant skills, so that they fail to ascend? No. We can track back women as better managers in the evolution of humankind, they were ‘nest defenders’ which is all about planning, allocating resources, communicating and coordinating the clan where they thrived. A successful organization not only requires right financials and raw materials, but a diligent handling of human resources. This requires emotional balance as it is all about handling a significant resource which is loaded with intelligence and lot of emotions. Women with elevated EQ than men handle this better. Here three cases of successful women managers in each category is discussed.

Women Manager are Better Communicators

Ms. Indra Nooyi – former CEO PepsiCo attributes her success to the communication she has with her employees which is a human skill. The Five C’s leadership principle of Ms. Indra Nooyi attributes importance to communication than competence, courage, confidence and a strong moral compass.

She communicates with her employees through a blog every week. She goes beyond this by writing letter to the employees, enquiring them, thanking their parents for the wonderful children who contributed to the success of PepsiCo India Pvt Ltd. She believes relationship building is important in an organization, and the employees should feel that they are been taken care by the organization for which they are working for. This relationship building and employee participation held together the employee moral when there were controversies about the brand. This is still getting reflected in the success of brand PepsiCo.

Women Managers are Better in Understanding the Employee Issues

Ms. Veena Kumaravel – Founder Naturals salon and beauty spa, a first generation women entrepreneur who excels in labor intense service industry.

Her principle of being successful manager is taking care of employee needs, so that they will take care of organization. This conceptual skill is a peculiar way of being a good manager. 15 years back, she created a training academy in Delhi, picked up people from north east of the country. They were unaware of the basics in beauty industry but they were trained in a residential academy and deployed across her salons in Tamilnadu. This happened when salon owners were searching for experienced service providers to work for them. She created her own set of loyal workforce. Once they were deployed in salons, their accommodation and food was taken care by the management and a considerable salary of the employees were sent back to their respective families as savings.

This addressed the operational issue of labor intense salon industry. Not only that, this created Naturals as a brand with low attrition rate and a franchisee friendly model. The brand owns 550+ salons in three categories, more than 10 training academies and the successful business model in which investors are willing to invest.

The Realistic Women Managers

Meghana Narayan and Shauravi Malik – Founder and CEO of Slurppfarm,

The ex JP morgan & McKinsey and company employees found a baby/kids food brand Slurppfarm with a very practical thought. They being mothers themselves, they tried to address the problem of how to provide healthy nutritious food to the children. They created a row of products with small millets as the major ingredient and marketed it with a tagline ‘Made by two mothers’. They hired mothers who are looking forward to restart their career after a childcare/maternity break into the organization. This technical expertise helped the organization to get the pulse of target audience and to design a better product as well as promotion.

This created a healthy snack brand, which attracted angel investment of \$188,000 and an expected revenue of \$4.5M

In spite of all these practical skills, nearly half of Indian women leave the workforce between junior and middle management levels. The major contributors for leaving are child care/maternity leave, sexual/workplace harassment and gender inequality.

Though female bosses create more employee engagement than the male bosses as suggested by a study, they feel the management is gender biased, which eventually ends in female bosses leaving the work environment.

Conclusion

This reflective research highlights the noteworthy ability of women managers and how it is reflected in the organization success. This being a sample study, there is a whole lot women entrepreneurs from SHG and MSME who are successfully running a profitable business for years together. According to Sixth Economic Census released by the Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, women constitute around 14% of the total entrepreneurship i.e. 8.05 million out of the total 58.5 million entrepreneurs. Among the states, the largest share in number of establishments under women entrepreneurship was held by Tamil Nadu (13.51%) followed by Kerala (11.35%), Andhra Pradesh (10.56%), West Bengal (10.33%) and Maharashtra (8.25%). With financial boost up from Government of India and schemes like TREAD (Trade Related Entrepreneurship Assistance and Development) Scheme, Mahila Udyam Nidhi Scheme, Annapurna Scheme, Stree Shakti Package for Women Entrepreneurs, Bhartiya Mahila Business Bank Loan, Dena Shakti will create a brighter and successful women entrepreneurs and managers.

A study by Business world on women entrepreneurs of India, shares though entrepreneurship among women is on rise, the challenges faced by them to sustain the business is much more than male entrepreneurs. Along with the expected setbacks like lack of finance, lack of raw materials, and workforce issues they have an additional humongous concern - gender bias.

Still strict women managers are termed as arrogant, haughty bosses. The women who juggle between family and work life is callously termed as selfish careless individual. The woman who moves up in the ladder of organization with sheer hard work is termed as flirty employee.

Said so, conducive, friendlier work environment which treats women as equivalent of male managers will bring in more successful women managers and organizations.

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